

Data sources and code for “Robots and the Rise of European Superstar Firms”

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1. Our firm-level data comes from the commercial database Amadeus which is provided by Bureau van Dijk. To access the data, researchers have to obtain a license of Amadeus by paying a subscription fee to Bureau van Dijk.

Website: <https://amadeus.bvdinfo.com>

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Amadeus includes financial data for European firms and provides all variables that are used in the estimation of production functions and information used to construct several control variables.

2. Information on the stock of robots is obtained from the World Robotics database which is released by the International Federation of Robotics (2016). The IFR records the installations of industrial robots on the basis of yearly surveys of nearly all industrial robot suppliers worldwide.

The data can be purchased from the IFR. For more information, see: <https://ifr.org/about-world-robotics/>

3. Other industry-level data

- OECD Stan: Employment data at industry level

- Eurostat: industry deflators

- Comtrade database: Information on imports and exports by industry

- To match trade level data, we use cross-walks from the World Bank (https://wits.worldbank.org/product_concordance.html) and Eurostat (http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/ramon/reactions/index.cfm?TargetUrl=LST_REL&StrLanguageCode=EN&IntCurrentPage=10)

See Appendix A1 for details.

- EU Klems: Information on ICT, R&D, Software etc.

Stata code: Do-Files

1. TFP and Markup estimation:

01_Summary_T1_TFPestimation.do:

- calculates TFP relative to industry mean in 2004 (for regressions).
- estimates different versions of production functions defined in e.g.

DLW_CD_GO_procedure.do (Cobb Douglas)

DLW_TL_GO_procedure.do (Translog)

- generates Dataset: datawork.dta used in further steps
- generates Table 1 (Summary Statistics)

01_Data_analysis_TFPabsolute.do:

- calculates absolute (non-demeaned) measure of TFP which is used to create figures

2. Combine different datasets and construct estimation sample:

02_Data_analysis_BuildSample.do:

generates dataset: datawork_regressions.dta which is used for main regressions

3. Regression tables:

Main results:

3_Regressions_T2_T3_T5_TFP_MU_Sales.do:

- generates results for TFP, markups and sales in Tables 2, Table 3, and Table 5

3_Regressions_T6_profits.do:

- generates results for profits in Table 6

3_Regressions_T7_Lshare.do:

Generates results for labour share in Table 7

Robustness checks:

3 Regressions_T4_C*.do:

- 7 separate do files for robustness checks (e.g.)

4. Figures:

4_Figures.do: generates Figures 1 – Figures 6